

SafeFetch

SafeFetch addresses double-fetch vulnerabilities in operating system kernels, which arise when the same user data is fetched multiple times without proper synchronization. Attackers can exploit these race conditions to escalate privileges or bypass security checks. SafeFetch introduces a lightweight per-syscall caching mechanism, ensuring consistency of kernel fetches and mitigating exploitation in real time. It improves both the coverage and performance of detection compared to earlier approaches, making it a practical defense for privileged software like kernels and hypervisors.

FATex (Firmware Analysis Toolkit)

FATex is RESCALE’s firmware analysis solution, designed to detect vulnerabilities in firmware images through both static and dynamic testing. It can emulate firmware in controlled environments, enabling testers to identify risks such as command injection, privilege escalation, or unsafe code execution. FATex provides a realistic execution environment and generates results that feed into the Dynamic Supply Chain Component Guarantee (DSCG). Its modular design allows it to be reused for a broad range of IoT and embedded firmware targets.

InSpectre Gadget

InSpectre Gadget focuses on Spectre-type microarchitectural vulnerabilities, which remain a major concern for modern CPUs. The tool scans kernels or hypervisors to discover potential gadgets, code patterns exploitable under the Spectre v2 threat model, and then analyzes their exploitability and severity. This enables a structured evaluation of low-level speculative execution risks, highlighting whether mitigations are effective. InSpectre Gadget thus provides deep insight into an attack surface that is still poorly understood but critical for system security.

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